

Munir's Taxonomy of Digital Learning

Note: Munir's Taxonomy of Digital Learning has received a commendation from international scholars at the PCF9 Conference, organized by the Commonwealth of Learning, in 2019.

Introduction

When it comes to the taxonomy of learning, Benjamin Bloom's name is at the forefront. For decades, academic institutions and scholars have been surrendering their expertise and yielding to the authority of Bloom.

The educational goals categorization framework proposed by Bloom and his collaborators presents a static, delusional, quantifying, controlling, and unresponsive structure, infused with an overwhelming vision of learning, and derived from a Western context. It suffers from hierarchical issues and has failed to adopt an inclusive and contextual approach. It offers sequential materialistic domains that are steeped in high expectations. Terms like complexity and specificity pose barriers to equitable learning practices. Similarly, categories such as knowledge and comprehension are regressive and not conducive to an open learning praxis.

Munir argues, "Learning is not always hierarchical and is instead situated in context. It is a flexible process, but Bloom's trajectory has failed to account for this reality. While knowledge is the basis for critical discussion, the act of recreation of knowledge is often ignored".

Bloom's taxonomy has undergone several revisions, which have led to an increase in doubts and complexity than simplicity. For example, Anderson and Krathwohl added the element of metacognition in the revised taxonomy. They shifted the concept of educational objectives to a classification, using verbs and gerunds, which resulted in a convoluted and complex framework. In the revised version, for instance, the verb 'remember' impedes deeper understanding and disengages new and prior knowledge. Overall, the concept of Lower Order Thinking Skills (LOTS) and Higher Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) is invasive to the learning inclusion in both the former and latter frameworks. These concepts significantly narrow our understanding of human intelligence and impede our ability to value the diversity of human perspectives.

Later, Andrew Churches developed a hierarchy of learning activities specifically for a digital environment, using a variety of new verbs. However, it has been criticized for overlooking the diversity of education settings, educational challenges, and access to digital resources, and for failing to improve digital literacy, ownership, and participation in the community of practice. Then, Krathwohl revised the taxonomy and proposed the use of digital technology, collaboration, and critical thinking skills.

Munir suggests, "It is essential to first assess the contextual state of digitalization and subsequently evaluate the availability and nature of digital resources within a specific setting before formulating a plan for digital learning. Above all, willingness and acceptance of embracing digitalization are crucial for which we need to facilitate individuals in understanding the vast potential of utilizing digital technology for learning purpose, and empower them to take ownership of their digital journey".

Munir's Digital Taxonomy of Learning proposes, "Individuals need to acquire basic digital skills to navigate online space effectively. This skill acquisition is essential to filter through the overwhelming amounts of information and apps available in the digital environment. Once a person has strengthened digital skills, they can develop digital literacy for experimenting and networking [resources and people] in an online learning environment. Unlike digital skills,

digital literacy focuses on understanding the contextual use of technology and how to communicate and participate flexibly within diverse online communities”.

Acquisition and participation are two distinct phases of the digital learning process. During the networking phase, individuals blur the boundaries between acquisition and participation, leveraging their digital literacy and skills to engage in reflexive praxis and peer review processes for filtration. This process requires ownership of learning and a willingness to engage in online discussions [with self and others]. Ultimately, the goal of Munir's Digital Taxonomy is to create and recreate knowledge within the digital learning environment.

This theory posits that individuals start their online journey as digital visitors but become digital residents after passing through phases [non-hierarchical] of the taxonomy. Once their dependencies shift, it results in inclusive, integrative, and innovative outcomes. Critical elements such as digital skills, digital literacy, ownership, and networking are crucial to accelerating digital learning.

This theory also recognizes the significance of low-cost technologies and Open Educational Resources as a means of facilitating both formal and informal learning.

<https://sites.google.com/view/munir-moosa-sadrudin>

Note: This model must be used in combination with **Munir's Permeable Digital Networking Model**